

TRENDS AND INNOVATIONS IN TEACHER EDUCATION IN CURRENT SCENARIO WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Today there are new expectations for education where the focus is on having teachers - be futurist leaders to ensure sustainable education. The key role of educational institutions is reflected in a variety of initiatives taken to transform the nature and function of education- both formal as well as non-formal. Universal accessibility to quality education is considered essential for development. This has necessitated improvement in the system of teacher education so as to prepare quality teachers. Teacher education is a program related with teacher proficiency and competence that would make them competent enough to face new challenges in the education. Development and changes in education have affected teacher education necessitating review and reforms. It demands understanding with investigative minds, assimilating the required transformations, accommodating and responding to the universal needs. We also need to train teachers with new perspectives as the outer world is in the classroom and schools are opening to the world. The pre-service and in-service teacher education programs have shown paradigm shift with its emphasis on globalization and individualization. This main purpose of this paper is to indicate main changes that has incurred in teacher education in India and also provide an overview of trends, reforms and innovations in teacher education (integrated teaching, teacher curriculum and teacher innovations). It also discusses the need of teacher education program to be innovative and various practices that can be included. It has been recognized that teacher education program should be structured and modified in a way that enables them to respond dynamically to the new problems and challenges in the field of education, then only teacher can help in national development.

INTRODUCTION

Teacher is the most important element in any educational, program and plays a central role in implementation of educational process at any stage. The level of achievement of learner is determined by teacher competence. So the quality of education basically depends on the quality of teachers. Kothari commission has very rightly said, "The destiny of India is being shaped in its classrooms." As the population in India is growing very rapidly day by day the need of well qualified and professionally trained teachers will also increase in the coming years. So lots of

efforts should be made to improve teacher education. Teacher education is a continuous process and its pre-service and in-service components are complimentary to each other. Education is instrumental in the preparation of teachers who can in their practice ensure transformative learning, where teacher and learner, learner and learner are co-constructors of knowledge.

Today there are new expectations for education where the focus is on having teachers- be futurist leaders to ensure sustainable education. The paradigm shift is 74 from teacher

dominated classroom practices to that of partnership between the teacher and the learners and their peers. The key role of educational institutions is reflected in a variety of initiatives taken to transform the nature and function of education—both formal as well as non-formal. Universal accessibility to quality education is considered essential for development. This has necessitated improvement in the system of teacher education so as to prepare quality teachers.

Trends and Innovations in Teacher Education : Present Scenario

India has a large system of education. There are nearly 5.98 lakh Primary Schools, 76 lakh Elementary Schools and 98 thousand High / Higher Secondary Schools in the country, about 1300 teacher education institutions for elementary teachers and nearly 700 colleges of education / university departments preparing teachers for secondary and higher secondary schools. Out of about 4.52 million teachers in the country nearly 3 million are teaching at the primary/elementary level. A sizeable number of them are untrained or under-trained. In certain regions, like the North-East, there are even unqualified teachers. As far as in-service education is concerned the situation is not very encouraging.

In this scenario it has been observed that teacher educators are not professionally committed and overall competencies of teachers leave much to be desired. The quality of pre-service education has actually shown signs of deterioration. Naseem & Anas (2011, pg. 187) in their study discussed about the various problems that are existing in Indian Teacher Education. While Sharma (2012) stressed on the fact that ICT can play a major role in professional growth of the teacher and shaping the global economy. Unless teacher educators model effective use of technology in their own classes, it will not be possible to prepare a new

generation of teachers who effectively use the new tools for teaching and learning.

All these problems are closely associated with increase in sub-standard institutions of teacher education and there are numerous reports of gross malpractices; and the support system provided by the State Councils of Educational Research and Training (SCERTs) and the University Departments of Education has been insufficient and there is no support system below the state level. The DIETs are charged with the responsibility of organizing pre-service and in-service programmes in addition to being the nodal resource centers for elementary education at district level. Likewise, Colleges of Teacher Education (CTEs) and Institutions of Advanced Study in Education (TASEs) have been given the responsibility of introducing innovations in teacher education programmes at the secondary and higher secondary stages and in vocational education. Although National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) as a non-statutory body has taken several steps as regards quality improvement in teacher education.

Its major contribution was to prepare Teacher Education Curriculum Framework consequently; teacher education curricula have witnessed many changes in teacher preparation programmes in various universities and boards in the country. During the last decade, new thrusts have been posed due to rapid changes in the educational, political, social and economic contexts at the national and international levels. Curriculum reconstruction has also become imperative in the light of some perceptible gaps in teacher education. Teacher education by and large, is conventional in its nature and purpose. The integration of theory and practice and consequent curricular response to the requirements of the school system still remains inadequate. Teachers are prepared in competencies and skills which do not necessarily equip them for becoming professionally effective. Their

familiarity with latest educational developments remains insufficient.

Organized and Emerging Trends and Innovation is usually understood as the introduction of something new and useful, like introducing new methods, techniques, or practices or new or altered products and services. Schools or teacher education institutions can carry out innovations or experimentation on any aspect of their work related to teaching-learning, training or management of schools in order to improve efficiency of the institution to overcome problems and difficulties, they face in day to day functioning. The present structure of teacher education is supported by a network of national, provincial and district level resource institutions working together to enhance the quality and effectiveness of teacher preparation programs at the pre-service level and also through in- service programs for serving teachers throughout the country.

Teacher education is now becoming more be to the emerging demands from the school system. Because the changing educational needs of the student and advancement in technology has widen the area of responsibilities of the teacher. Now teachers has to perform various roles like encouraging, Supporting and facilitating in teaching-learning situations which enables learners (students) to discover their talents, to realize their physical and intellectual potentialities to the fullest, to develop character

and desirable social and human values to function as responsible citizens.

CONCLUSION

Since the teacher is the pivot of the entire educational system and is the main catalytic agent for introducing desirable changes in the teaching learning process, all attempts need be made for motivating teachers to become innovative and creative. It goes without saying that a self motivated and really industrious teacher can utilize his own resources to keep himself abreast of new knowledge and skills. It has been recognized that teacher education program should be structured and modified in a way that enables them to respond dynamically to the new problems and challenges in the field of education, then only teacher can help in national development.

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